

TEACHING VOCABULARY BY USING REALIA MEDIA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8084738>

Abstract: This study aims to describe how realia applied by English teacher in their classroom, as realia media has significant role in improving the vocabulary of the students. The students feel afraid to speak in English because of their less word of vocabulary. Realia media is the one simple interesting media that may bring motivation for the student who afraid to study English. Teacher of English can use realia media and bring it in the class to get more attention, and participation of students.

Keywords: realia, effective media, teaching English, teaching vocabulary, real-life object.

English is one of the most important languages in the world. It is not only used as an international language but also it is used to access the science and technology. Based on Brown (2000), language is a system of arbitrary conventionalized vocal, written, gesture symbol that enable members of given community to communicate intelligibly with one another; one of the aspects of language is vocabulary.

Vocabulary is an important fundamental aspect, when the students learn a foreign language, especially English language. The first thing we have to know is vocabulary. According to Hedge (2000) states that there is a lack of attention to vocabulary. In this case, learning about vocabulary topic is important mean to express out thought and feeling, either in spoken and written form (p.110-111).

English vocabulary can help students to control their abilities in listening, speaking, writing, and reading. Nation (2002) affirms that vocabulary growth is such an important part of language acquisition that it deserves to be planned for, controlled and monitored.

As nowadays, English is considered to be the favorite subject added to the curriculum. However, some problems arise from the schools such as the lack of facility, classroom management, books and the educational background of the teachers. In the aspect of classroom, management is about media, method or technique. It is important to set the classroom to be fun and to be interesting. One of the efforts of making interesting teaching learning process is taking real object to the classroom. This technique is called realia. Realia is various kind of visual, which can be effectively by EFL. Realia provides real-life object to classroom.

Teaching language needs good and interesting media. Media used in the teaching learning activity will keep the learner focus on the teacher, thus the classroom will be on teacher's control. The media used should be effective and interesting; Suyanto (2007: 6.4) said that the use of effective and interesting media in teaching can help the students understand the material easily. There are kinds of media can be used in the teaching learning English to learners, they are: flashcards; diagram; chart; poster; video/film; animation; audio; power point; smart board; puppet; realia.

The creativity of the teacher will give functions to the media used. If a teacher brings a rose or sunflower, a rabbit or a cat, a stove or a pan, into a classroom to help her/him in teaching, she/he is using realia. Realia helps to make English language input as comprehensible as possible and to build "an associative bridge between the classroom and the world" (Heaton, 1979 in Smith, 1997). Learners can directly connect the language to the objects mentioned in

the material. By having realia in the classroom, young learners can develop their multi-sensor function by experiencing the learning “through seeing, hearing, touching, and manipulating” items (Rivers (1983, in Smith, 1997). The teaching learning process will be effective and enjoyable, and most of all they will not forget the activities in the classroom.

There are advantages of presenting realia in the teaching learning process:

- Kinesthetic learning is the type of learning that students will most effectively acquire, mostly because they will have hands-on experience.
- The use of realia brings a welcome change in the class, a break from typical class activities like reading and writing.
- The unexpectedness of having to suddenly interact with real objects will keep students on their toes; it will create excitement, and they’ll have fun.
- Students have the chance to practice real life situations like using maps and asking for directions in a foreign language, but with the guidance of someone who speaks fluently and will help them get it right. Once they hit the street, they will feel more confident in speaking the language with the locals.
- Students will clearly understand the reason they’re learning a particular ESL component.

Instead of wondering when and where they might have use for a particular language element, they’ll know the reason. (Smith, 1997)

Drinkwater suggested the use of realia in teaching English to young learners, she used tennis ball, dried bean, plastic bags, scarf and many others to help learners to connect between words and objects.

A research done by Chiarantano (2005) proved that Using realia in the EFL classroom serves to foster a more creative and active teaching-learning environment and promotes cultural understanding. The realia used in the teaching learning should be appropriate with the material and the learners’ condition.

Here we suggest some realia used for teaching English to learners as mention below.

- to teach vocabulary for animals, clothing, fruit, use actual objects or facsimiles thereof (pieces of clothing, toy animals, plastic fruit). For young learners, it's a very useful tool in making the abstract concrete.
- to introduce learners to USA (or countries) use a USA flag, a map of the world, and photographs of USA. Create a picture of a country, introduce and practice target vocabulary and sentence patterns (for example: I'm from Uzbekistan), and serve as a springboard to compare and contrast USA with Uzbekistan (Uzbekistan is part of Central Asia. USA is in North)
- to teach prepositions of place (such as on, in, under, next to, in front of, over). Objects can be placed on a desk, in a desk, under a desk and so on.
- to create a dialogue using the present simple tense and present perfect tense use (Uzbek Navruz holiday)
- to tell a story use Christmas cards as a means to explain the concept of Christmas and some of its many traditions, to illustrate Christmas images such as Santa Claus, reindeer, candy cane, Christmas trees, poinsettia and to teach Christmas greetings such as "Merry Christmas and a Happy New Year. Christmas cards provided a springboard to get my students to talk about their own holidays and customs.

So realia media could improve the vocabulary of students and it more effective and easy media that can brought in the class or we can use this media to get the students know about things around them, example when they go to the museum, teacher also can show them about real object. In case of it, because when the writer did the research there are less motivation and participation activity of students then, the writer would like to suggest the teacher to use realia media as one of learning media in learning activity especially in teaching vocabulary.

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